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Societal Challenges and the Green Deal in Europe Post-Coronavirus

Part of the Collection: Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes

October 2025

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Executive summary of recommendations

This report, based on 24 local social experiments across six European Green Deal priority areas (Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Food, Sustainable Mobility, and Preserving Biodiversity), examines how post-coronavirus societal challenges can drive, accelerate, or hinder progress in implementation. It also considers the feedback and interrelationships among these streams, as well as the role of key actors in advancing sustainability transitions. Based on the findings that focus on the landscape level developments (i.e. external societal pressures and challenges, such as climate change and major geopolitical events) we present recommendations to strengthen response capacity and systemic resilience at both regime (i.e. dominant systems of governance, infrastructure, policy, and markets) and niche levels (i.e. local or experimental spaces where alternative practices and innovations can emerge).

Embed anticipatory governance into transition strategies.

Institutions are required to be better prepared for navigating uncertainty by detecting and responding to early signals of disruption and opportunity. Anticipatory governance mechanisms, which can include e.g. participatory foresight; community visioning, community-based scenario planning, and flexible support program design for local actors, can help align short-term response with long-term transformation. These tools are especially valuable in volatile contexts shaped by geopolitical and ecological instability.

Strengthen institutional responsiveness and local intermediation.

Regime actors should develop more agile delivery systems, particularly in key policy areas as identified by the Green Deal, e.g. support for clean energy, housing renovation, sustainable mobility, circular economy, sustainable food (farm to fork), and preserving biodiversity (includes nature restoration). Trusted local intermediaries, e.g. renovation advisors or 'transition coordinators' – a new role for local (municipality) staff – can bridge the gap between institutional intent and lived reality. Simplifying procedures and improving continuity in public service delivery helps rebuilding trust and enabling broader participation of citizens.

Support niche-level innovation and collective capacity.

Community-led initiatives frequently demonstrate the ability to experiment, mobilise, and respond under pressure. These niche-level innovations should receive long-term support (not just short-term pilot funding) including legal recognition, improved local infrastructures and capacity-building. Informal but essential social resources (such as mutual aid, community learning, and care work) should be valued and supported through targeted programmes.

Align incentives and infrastructure with everyday practices.

Sustainability practices are shaped not by awareness alone, but by structural conditions such as transport access, housing stock, care responsibilities, and digital connectivity. Additionally, both living and non-living non-human actors – such as nature, animals, plants, weather events, and socio-material infrastructure should be accounted for when identifying barriers or enablers of change. Co-design processes involving citizens as end-users can ensure that interventions are practical and inclusive. Policy incentives must better reflect these material and social realities.

Reframe transition narratives and rebuild political trust.

Transition communication must go beyond climate targets to engage with people's lived concerns (e.g. health, comfort, financial security, and local benefit). Storytelling about successful grassroots initiatives can counter top-down narratives and increase public legitimacy. EU and national institutions should prioritise fairness and transparency in communication, while supporting municipal-level learning and shared narrative-building.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Introducing the project

This report presents findings from **cross-topic comparisons, scaling and synthesis**, of the project ‘*Social sciences and Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable Green Deal*’ (SHARED GREEN DEAL). The European Green Deal is a programme of policies aimed at overcoming climate change and environmental degradation by transforming the European Union (EU) into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy. The goal of SHARED GREEN DEAL is to stimulate behavioural, social and cultural change across Europe, aligned with the policy priorities of the Green Deal.

SHARED GREEN DEAL provides Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) tools to support the implementation of the Green Deal programme. In the past, SSH research on green transitions has focused on changes to either individuals (‘micro’ phenomena) or systems and collectives (‘macro’ phenomena). In contrast, SHARED GREEN DEAL focuses on ‘middle range’ (‘meso’) changes to bridge these two sets of understandings and priorities (Foulds et al., 2025a). Using this innovative ‘meso’ approach, the project links societal actors to foster knowledge sharing, learn from collective experiences, and feed back into ‘macro’ policies and governance.

The SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium brings together 22 leading organisations from across Europe, including universities, research institutions, network organisations and businesses. The project is structured around **six priority Green Deal topics: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Preserving Biodiversity**. Within these six themes, a total of 24 social experiments (Figure 1.1) were delivered across different EU Member States and affiliated countries between April 2023 and June 2024, working with local municipalities and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) (Table A1.1¹ in the Appendix). These are called ‘local partners’, and they carried out the social experiments autonomously, with the consortium partners providing initial training and guidance, as well as support whenever needed. Other resources related to the running of and impacts from the social experiments can be found via www.sharedgreendeal.eu.

¹ Further detail about each of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments can be found in the project’s Case Study Guides (Kovács et al., 2024).

Figure 1.1. Map of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments (Kovács et al., 2024)

1.2. Introducing the report

This report is based on a secondary analysis of data from the social experiments with the **main objective to identify how Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) priority themes cut across all six experiment streams**. The SSH priority themes are: (1) Gender and Diversity; (2) Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities; (3) Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19; (4) Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions; (5) Geographic Differences and Evolutions across Time.

This report focuses on **Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19** and how these can drive, accelerate, or hinder progress in implementing the Green Deal. Our analysis also considers the feedback and interrelationships among six Green Deal's priority topics. Alongside this report, four other reports were published on the respective SSH priority themes.

For the secondary analyses, a variety of data sources, collected within the social experiments, were considered (Table 1.2 below). Table A1.1 and Table A1.2 (in the Appendix) provide an overview of the social experiments streams and summarise the data sources in more detail, respectively.

Table 1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis²

Data source (#DS)	Provided by
#DS1: WP4 Codebooks of interview data with social experiments participants	SGD consortium members (WP4)
#DS2: Monthly survey (WP5 questions)	Local partners
#DS3: Monthly meeting notes (including 12th meeting)	SGD consortium members
#DS4: Final reflective surveys and experiments' journeys (Responsible Research & innovation (RRI) material)	Local partners
#DS5: RRI interviews with consortium partners	SGD consortium members
#DS6: Applications of Local Partners to host social experiments	Local partners
#DS7: Green Deal Topic Webinars	SGD consortium members

Although all data sources were reviewed, not all were equally relevant for all SSH priority themes. For this report, the data sources #DS1 (WP4 interview codebooks), #DS2 (monthly surveys), #DS3 (monthly meeting notes), and #DS4 (final reflective surveys) were found particularly relevant to explore patterns of societal challenges across the streams and their impact on advancing sustainability transitions towards a strong Green Deal.

1.3. Introducing Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19

The theme 'Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19' explores the social, economic, and political dynamics that have shaped European societies since the World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 a pandemic on 11 March 2020. On 5 May 2023, the WHO declared the end of the public health emergency caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, just one month after the SHARED GREEN DEAL project's social experiments had begun (April 2023), at a time when public perceptions of

² A more detailed version can be found in Table A1.2, in the Appendix.

these challenges were already shifting, as we will show later (see Figure 1.3a). This report focuses therefore on the societal challenges related to the post-coronavirus period in Europe.

Societal challenges, being inherently complex and wicked problems (Lawrence et al., 2022; Rittel & Webber, 1973), can be framed under the *Grand Societal Challenges* (Bina et al., 2017) that have shaped Europe’s research agendas (e.g. FP 7, Horizon 2020) and, more recently, the mission-oriented policy approach of the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2024; European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation & Mazzucato, 2018). The Europe’s Mission approach launched in 2019 aims to drive the continent’s transformation toward a greener, healthier, more inclusive, and resilient future, as envisioned in the Green Deal, by informing policy through research and innovation strategies aligned with five major thematic missions addressing grand societal challenges. The five EU Missions are: (1) Adaptation to Climate Change, (2) Cancer, (3) Restore our Ocean and Waters, (4) 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030, (5) Healthy soils. These five missions’ design and implementation are also framed by the Sustainable Development Goals and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Table 1.3 (see below) illustrates how each of the five EU Missions aligns with key objectives of the European Green Deal, highlighting their contributions across the six thematic areas under analysis in this report: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Food, Sustainable Mobility, and Preserving Biodiversity.

Table 1.3. Alignment of EU Missions with European Green Deal Objectives

EU Mission	Relevant Green Deal Objectives
Adaptation to Climate Change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Clean Energy & Sustainable Mobility – Supports infrastructure resilience and energy efficiency ▪ Circular Economy – Promotes resource-saving designs and waste reduction in adaptation projects
Cancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable Food & Clean Energy – Indirectly linked through the health-environment nexus (e.g., reduced pollution, safe and healthier diets); more aligned with broader public health goals, namely cancer reduction and mitigation.
Restore our Ocean and Waters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Preserving Biodiversity – Protects aquatic ecosystems and restores marine/freshwater biodiversity ▪ Circular Economy – Promotes sustainable use of marine resources (e.g., microplastics reduction)
100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Clean Energy & Sustainable Mobility – Focus on zero-emissions transport and smart grids ▪ Efficient Renovations – Upgrades buildings to meet energy targets ▪ Circular Economy – Promotes urban regeneration and resource efficiency
Healthy Soils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable Food – Supports organic farming and soil fertility (aligned with the Farm to Fork Strategy) ▪ Preserving Biodiversity – Restores habitats and soil ecosystems (aligned with the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030) ▪ Circular Economy – Emphasises nutrient cycling and waste reduction

These five missions are solution-oriented responses to societal challenges and are closely aligned with the European Green Deal, working as mechanisms aimed at realising a vision of a sustainable, climate-neutral, and resilient Europe. However, their implementation has been shaped, and at times disrupted, by evolving social, economic, and political dynamics accelerated since the COVID-19 outbreak. These include the digitalisation of provisioning systems, advances in Internet of Things and Artificial Intelligence, changing work patterns, debates on the four-day workweek, and a revival of older urban planning ideas such as the 15-minute city, just to name a few. Additionally, new and unexpected geopolitical concerns have emerged, notably the Ukraine-Russia conflict, which since 24 February 2022 has reawakened fears around nuclear risks, unstable global energy and resources geopolitics, further complicating collective efforts to address long-term societal challenges. These concerns come in addition to the devastating effects of the war itself (e.g. casualties, forced migration, and reduced access to essential resources and adequate living conditions). The conflict in the Middle East, specifically Israel's war on Gaza in response to the Hamas attack in October 2023, is another major source of geopolitical tension and humanitarian catastrophe. From June 2025, this tension was further exacerbated by the conflict spreading to Iran (also known as the Twelve-Day War). The rise of populism and Trump's reelection as president of the United States of America in November 2024 have further impacted global politics. These conflicts have significantly affected Europe's foreign policy position and military spending, while also contributing to increased social polarisation and a rise in both antisemitic and anti-Muslim incidents.

Other developments that these conflicts have worsened include the energy and food insecurity crises combined with the rise of inflation rates, peaking at 11.5% in October 2022 (European Commission, 2023), and the European Central Bank policies to control inflation, namely through the rise of interest rates, which peaked at 4% in September 2023 (ECB³). Some of the visible effects are: difficulties in accessing an adequate diet, the dilemma faced by the most vulnerable groups between paying energy bills or buying food and growing challenges in paying mortgages and affording housing (UNDP, 2025). Other important dynamics⁴ revolve around threats to democracy (e.g. increase of populist discourse in various media, notably social media, which favour the restriction of the rights of political, racial, ethnic and other social groups). These threats take concrete form by the election of far-right and populist party representatives to parliaments and government leadership across parts of Europe.

These challenges are also reflected in the latest Eurobarometer (European Commission & IPSOS, 2024), which was conducted between June and July 2024, a period that coincided with the final phase of the social experiments of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project and mirrored the overall public perception of societal challenges at that moment in time. According to the Eurobarometer (ibid., Figure 1.3a), it was observed that the top challenge facing the EU, according to 50% of respondents, is the war in Ukraine. Other major concerns include irregular migration (41%), environmental issues and climate change (35%), cost of living (32%), and terrorism/security (29%). Additional issues cited by about 1 in 5 respondents include social inequalities (21%), the Middle East conflict (20%), low economic growth (19%), and disinformation (19%). Only 8% view digital technologies' societal impact as a key challenge.

3 Cf. https://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/policy_and_exchange_rates/key_ecb_interest_rates/html/index.pt.html, accessed 2nd June 2025.

4 For a contextualization of what happened in Europe and the World during the social experiments' period of April 2023-June 2024, Britannica provides timelines of the major socio-geopolitical and environmental events in those years. For 2023, see <https://www.britannica.com/topic/2023-The-Year-in-Review>; for 2024 see <https://www.britannica.com/topic/2024-Year-in-Review>.

Which of the following do you think are the current main challenges the EU is facing? Please select up to three answer. [Multiple Answers]

Figure 1.3a. Responses to the Flash Eurobarometer 550, question 4 on the current main challenges the EU is facing (n=25658).

Source: Adapted by the authors based on the European Commission & IPSOS (2024).

This multilayer of social, political and economic problems aggravated by the consequences of the global pandemic due to COVID-19 and related sanitary risks and the Ukraine war coexist with the triple planetary crisis of climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss that goes in tandem with social inequalities in Global and European societies (European Environmental Agency, 2024; Siirilä et al. 2024). A useful visualization of the interconnected global risks and their perception is provided in the Global Risks Reports 2023 and 2024 (World Economic Forum, 2023, 2024), which also show shifts in perception (Figure 1.3b). For example, whereas in 2023 the cost of living-crisis connects, among others, to the natural resource crisis, in 2024 they were replaced by other crises, being the crises of social polarization and lack of economic opportunity perceived as the major societal concerns by then.

Global Risks Report 2023

Global risks landscape: an interconnections map

Source: World Economic Forum, Global Risks Perception Survey 2022-2023

Global Risks Report 2024

Global risks landscape: an interconnections map

Source: World Economic Forum Global Risks Perception Survey 2023-2024.

Figure 1.3b. Comparison of Global risks landscape in 2023 and 2024.
Source: (World Economic Forum, 2023, 2024). Reproduced with permission.

The global COVID-19 pandemic can therefore be regarded as a liminal period that, with its official end, marks a turning point characterised by heightened social volatility. In this report, we focus on the societal aspects that were most prominent during the period of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments. Furthermore, while societal challenges are often shaped by governance agendas, such as policy formulation and resource allocation (see report on the SSH priority theme Governance (Gray et al., 2025a), in this collection), this report focuses solely on the societal challenges themselves. We define these boundaries intentionally to avoid significant overlap with other SSH priority themes. Where relevant, we highlight potential connections and bridges to those themes.

Societal challenges are complex and with no clearly defined boundaries. The Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19 SSH theme seeks to understand and analyse the results of the social experiments considering these various social, political and economic dynamics, and their impact on advancing (or blocking) the implementation of the Green Deal.

2. Conceptual and methodological approach

2.1. Conceptual lens

The challenges described above impact society at large, often requiring innovative solutions that transcend institutional and geographical boundaries (e.g. Europe's mission topics like climate change and healthy soils, which intersect with poverty, inequality, and political polarisation). We conceptualise societal challenges based on the Horizon2020 Grand Societal Challenges (GSC) framing (Bina et al., 2017) as complex, multi-level, and multi-dimensional wicked problems (Rittel & Webber, 1973) that require concerted efforts from various actors, including public, private, and non-profit organisations, to address them effectively (Voegtlin et al., 2022).

Sustainability Transitions theories – especially the Multi-Level Perspective (MLP) (Geels, 2002, 2024; Smith et al., 2010) – and Social Practice Theory (SPT) (Schatzki, 1996; Shove et al., 2012)⁵ offer complementary lenses for analysing societal challenges and change dynamics aligned with the European Green Deal. These frameworks help reveal how structural conditions, agency, and everyday practices interact to shape systemic transformation (Keller et al. 2022) and were therefore found relevant for our analysis, since they guided our findings' interpretation.

The Multi-Level Perspective (MLP) conceptualises transitions across three levels: landscape (external pressures like climate change or geopolitical crises, such as a military conflict), regime (dominant systems of practices, policies, and technologies), and niche (spaces where innovations emerge) (see Figure A2.1 in the Appendix). Change occurs through interactions across these levels; however, in this report, we focus particularly on moments when landscape pressures destabilise the dominant regime and open space for niche and alternative innovations (our 24 experiments are instances of such innovations). In other words, societal challenges such as climate change, economic instability, and geopolitical tensions act as landscape-level pressures (Morone et al., 2016) that destabilise regimes and create windows of opportunity for innovation. While disruptive, such pressures can open space for niche alternatives and shift public routines and expectations.

However, this process is not automatic. Whether societal challenges enable transformation depends on how actors – such as policymakers, civil society, and citizens – respond. It also involves the role of non-human actors⁶, including technologies, infrastructures, nature and material resources that shape what practices are possible or likely, depending on access to e.g., transport networks, energy grids, biodiverse landscapes. Here, Social Practice Theory (SPT) offers important insights, as it captures how societal challenges interweave in everyday practices and how both human and non-human actors influence systems like food, energy, and mobility.

⁵ For an explanation of these two theoretical frameworks please see Foulds et al. (2025a). For an introduction to transition theories see the report by SHARED GREEN DEAL colleagues (Krijgsman et al., 2023). For a brief account of practice theory and gender see the report on the SSH priority theme Gender in this collection (Aggeli et al., 2025).

⁶ For further reflection on non-human actors see Latour (1996) as well as Price & Chao (2023) who discuss living and non-living actors, as well as similar idioms such as more-than-human, other-than-human, beyond-human, among others.

Recent work (Keller et al., 2022) has combined MLP and SPT to examine how practices, niches, regimes and landscapes intersect. This allows us to analyse how societal challenges are embedded in daily life while also reflecting broader landscape shifts that shape the feasibility of Green Deal objectives. Building on this, we adopt a cross-fertilisation approach that identifies where transitions can be triggered by targeting key friction points. According to Keller et al. (2022) these friction points can reflect enduring misalignments between landscape-regime-niche practices that can hinder change. The concept of windows of opportunity is another germane term useful in our analysis. These windows open when pressures from the landscape level (e.g. economic, environmental, or geopolitical crises) intersect with internal regime tensions, creating conditions that enable the emergence of innovative (niche) practices and initiatives (Geels & Schot, 2007)⁷.

Using this conceptual lens, our secondary data analysis focuses on identifying patterns of societal challenges and their distribution across the six Green Deal streams; the multi-layered dynamics and practices shaped by landscape pressures, namely the interplay of challenges that foster or hinder change. We also examine the key actors driving or obstructing societal transformation toward the Green Deal implementation. This includes identifying the inflexibility of practices and lock-in mechanisms, enacted by both human and non-human actors, such as sociotechnical infrastructures that span across food, mobility, and energy systems.

2.2. Methodology

Our analytical approach to these societal challenges was guided by three research questions (RQ):

- RQ1: What are the main patterns and dynamics of societal challenges seen in the experiment material? [**Patterns and interrelationship dynamics**]
- RQ2: Which societal challenges accelerate, facilitate or hinder the achievement of Green Deal objectives? [**Feedback dynamics**]
- RQ3: Who are the main actors that may drive such change? [**Actors**]

First, a preliminary thematic content inductive analysis, focused on the local partners' answers to the monthly survey's societal challenges related questions (see #DS2 in Table A1.2, in the Appendix), was conducted through the MAXQDA 2024 word exploring functions. Three main themes emerged from the data concerning the major social, economic and political dynamics, identified by the local partners, that are impacting European contemporary societies: (i) the environmental crises (e.g. biodiversity crisis, climate change and sustainable infrastructure), (ii) the geopolitical tensions (e.g. Ukraine war, the political tensions and uncertainties and associated supply chain disruptions) and (iii) the cost of living (e.g. economic pressure on small business, inflation and interest rates). These topics are aligned with the major topics identified in the Eurobarometer of 2024 (section 1.3.).

Our analysis process then followed a first round of deductive coding of the interview codebooks (#DS1), the monthly survey material (#DS2) and the 12th monthly meeting notes (#DS3) (see Table A1.2, in the Appendix). For this step, we developed a simple deductive coding scheme – based on the main societal challenge patterns which were preliminarily identified in the data (environmental crises, geopolitical tensions⁸ and cost of living) and the dynamics (#facilitation/#hindrance) that these societal challenge patterns establish in relation to the achievement of the Green Deal

⁷ For other sources of windows of opportunity beyond landscape pressures see (Aarhaug & Tveit, 2023).

⁸ It is important to mention that although migration related issues are identified in the Eurobarometer (section 1.3.) as one of the main European societal challenges (see Figure 1.3a), this was not a predominant theme that emerged from our data (except for Sustainable Mobility with references to refugees from the Ukrainian war).

objectives. Also, in a more inductive approach we set up an open coding structure to identify the different actors that emerged from the data and that may enact such change.

Table 2.2. Simplified coding scheme for the societal challenges analysis: Overview of thematic categories and the respective codes applied.

Category	Code	Description
Societal Challenges patterns	Environmental crises	Segments which mention social, economic and political dynamics that impact European contemporary societies such as the biodiversity crisis, climate change and sustainable infrastructure
	Cost of living	Segments which mention social, economic and political dynamics that impact European contemporary societies e.g. economic pressure on small business, inflation and interest rates
	Geopolitical tensions	Segments which mention the social, economic and political dynamics that are impacting European contemporary societies such as military conflicts (e.g. Ukraine, Gaza), migration, refugees, the political tensions and uncertainties and supply chain disruptions
Dynamics	Hinder	Segments which mention societal challenges hindering the achievement of the Green Deal objectives
	Facilitator/accelerator	Segments which mention societal challenges facilitating or accelerating the achievement of the Green Deal objectives
Actors	Actors	Open sub-coding of this code according to the actors that emerge from the data and that may enact such change

In a second round of coding, and building upon the previous coded segments, we proceeded to identify illustrative quotes that reveal the patterns, dynamics (feedbacks) and interrelationships between the different six core Green Deal topics in light of various societal challenges, while also systematising the actors through the conceptual lens aforementioned (section 2.1.). During this process, and emphasising the iterative approach to refine our coding, several reflective team discussions were conducted, assuring intercoder reliability.

3. Societal Challenges: patterns, dynamics, and actors

First, we present an overview of the main societal challenges patterns identified in the data and zoom into each societal challenges' category by exploring streams' interrelationships dynamics (RQ1). Next, we present results on the stream's feedback dynamics by looking at drivers and barriers regarding the Green Deal's implementation, friction points and related windows of opportunity (RQ2). Finally, we systemise the actors and their position in these complex dynamics, with a focus on their role in advancing change towards the Green Deal's objectives (RQ3).

3.1. Overview of main societal challenges patterns

In total, 966 text segments from a variety of data sources were coded in MAXQDA (see Table A3.1a, Table A3.1b and Table A3.1c on code frequencies, in the Appendix). Figure 3.1a (below) gives an overview of the general distribution of the societal challenges coded as 'geopolitical tensions', 'environmental crises' and 'cost of living', for the whole data set, with 'cost of living' being the most frequent code in our sample. Overall, the distribution shows a moderately even spread, with no single category being overwhelmingly dominant.

Figure 3.1a. Percentage of all coded segments per societal challenges (n=966).
Source: Coding of the social experiments data – monthly survey material, the 12th monthly meeting notes and the interview codebooks (for the code frequency see Tables 3.1a/b/c, in the Appendix).

However, a more nuanced picture emerges when examining societal challenges patterns across the different social experiment streams: concerns about the cost of living are particularly prominent in Efficient Renovations, Clean Energy, and Circular Economy, while environmental crises are more salient in Preserving Biodiversity and Sustainable Mobility (Figure 3.1b).

References to geopolitical tensions were made in all experiment streams, in particular in Sustainable Food (33.3 %, n = 14, see Figure 3.1b below and Table A3.1d in the Appendix, respectively) though overall less frequently than other societal challenges.

Figure 3.1b. Percentage of the main societal challenges coded segments per stream (n=709).
Source: Coding of the social experiments interview codebooks.

Looking at the perceptions of local partners whether they felt that the challenges related to economic, geopolitical or ecological crises affected their experiments, the Circular Economy stream felt most affected and the Preserving Biodiversity stream least affected by these challenges (see Table 3.1 below, based on #DS2 Monthly Surveys, and Table A3.1d, in the Appendix). Furthermore, it can be noted that experiments in urban contexts show a clearer pattern of being affected, particularly via economic routes (e.g. inflation, energy poverty, material cost), while in rural contexts respondents indicated being less affected by these challenges, with environmental disruptions – such as extreme weather events – being the predominant challenge.

Table 3.1. Summary of the answers from Monthly Surveys (#DS2) to the question: 'In the past two months of running the experiment, in what ways have you encountered any experiment-related difficulties or opportunities linked to the current / recent economic, geopolitical, and ecological crises?'

Experiment Stream	Context	Affected	Not Affected	N/A (non-applicable or no response)	Key Observations
Clean Energy	Rural (2)*	4	2	3	Energy prices, grant delays; vulnerable households
	Mixed (2)	7	4	0	Urban-rural inequalities, policy friction
Circular Economy	Urban (3)	17	11	5	Cost-of-living raised interest in reuse; space/time limitations in cities
	Mixed (1)	4	3	2	Strong local demand but uneven capacity
Efficient Renovations	Urban (2)	4	3	3	Inflation, material costs, funding issues
	Rural (2)	3	2	3	Delays in accessing renovation support
Sustainable Food	Urban (1)	4	1	1	City logistics, vulnerable groups affected
	Rural (1)	2	0	1	Agricultural risk, drought, pests
	Mixed (2)	3	1	2	Hybrid food systems impacted by pricing/logistics
Sustainable Mobility	Urban (4)	4	4	3	Mixed effects: some noted weather and cost barriers, others saw stable or increased engagement
Preserving Biodiversity	Urban (2)	1	2	1	Climate discourse helped to raise interest
	Rural (2)	2	4	3	Less direct disruption, more long-term awareness
Total		55	37	45	137

*number on rural/urban refers to experiment sites

Out of 137 responses, 45 were categorised as 'n/a' (non-applicable or no response). These include cases in which the question regarding crisis-related difficulties or opportunities was left unanswered, explicitly marked as 'n/a' or 'none' or where the content focused solely on operational updates such as meeting organisation, stakeholder engagement, or logistical progress without reference to broader economic, geopolitical, or ecological conditions. These entries may reflect that the crisis context was not perceived as relevant, while other respondents suggest a possible hesitation in connecting global issues to the experiment's local context or just signs of reporting fatigue.

3.2. Societal challenges' interrelationships dynamics across social experiments

In this section, we look at the interrelationships' dynamics observed in the social experiments' responses to the previously identified societal challenges.

Overall, it can be noted that there is a perceived multiplicity of crises, aligned with the understanding of polycrisis (European Environmental Agency, 2024). For example, COVID-19, the Ukraine war, climate change, and the cost of living crisis are not seen as isolated events but as an interconnected set of 'landscape' pressures that have impact on people's lives and decision-making processes at the local level:

“First the COVID pandemic delayed renovations largely and then the Ukraine–Russia conflict made the prices of construction materials go up a lot, making renovation much more difficult.”

[Efficient Renovations, Spain, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 66)]

“We have found impacts related to the war and supply chain issues still existing from COVID exacerbating challenges...”

[Sustainable Mobility, Ireland, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 121)]

“Coronavirus, the Ukraine–Russia conflict, climate change impacts, cost of living crisis, or political issues are all relevant... People are influenced consciously and subconsciously.”

[Circular Economy, Slovenia, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 16)]

“Both the climate change crisis in agriculture and uncertainties at the geopolitical level have highly incentivised the adoption of regulative derogation related to pesticide use. [...]Difficulties in raw agricultural goods supplies have made regulative derogation more acceptable. This reflects the possibility to use pesticides with a high-risk profile at our local level.”

[Sustainable Food, Italy, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 97)]

This multiplicity of crises can be observed across all streams. Next, we zoom in into coded data for the respective societal challenge applying our conceptual lens as outlined in Section 2.1.

3.2.1. Insights about ‘cost of living’

Interview data coded under ‘**cost of living**’ reveal that rising living expenses are among the most frequently cited and structurally significant societal challenges, affecting decisions across energy, housing, consumption, and daily mobility. While one visible pattern in the analysed data was the framing of affordability concerns as temporary distractions from environmental goals, there were also instances where these concerns were portrayed as deeply rooted barriers capable of constraining even the most motivated individuals. One participant noted that sustainable consumption is impacted negatively by decreased purchasing power:

“Social pressure, loss in purchasing power... many topics take precedence against ecology. I find it both sad and dangerous, because it will be more complicated to find organic farmers tomorrow if we abandon them, instead of supporting them despite the crisis, until the consumers return to responsible purchases.” [Circular Economy, France, Local Participant, Agricultural Engineer, 51yo, Woman⁹, #DS1 (No. 6)]

Taking our conceptual lens, this reflects landscape-level economic pressures – inflation, energy market volatility, wage stagnation – that reinforce regime inertia (i.e. business as usual) and delay the adoption of circular or low-carbon alternatives. The rising energy prices and bills are a major concern, especially for low-income households and those in energy-inefficient homes (see also the report on the SSH theme Justice and Vulnerability in this collection (Bharucha, 2025)).

These broad pressures are shaping socio-technical transitions across Europe and can also push people into survival-mode pragmatism, as seen in the comment by one of the entrepreneurs in the Circular Economy social experiments:

“You may also want to make things happen, and to do ethical things because it resonates with you. That’s what I want... But if I cannot earn enough money to make a living, then there is not much I can do.” [Circular Economy, France, Local Participant, Home and Office Organizer and Zero Waste Upcycler, 43yo, Woman, #DS1 (No. 7)]

While ethical values may remain strong, the infrastructure, pricing, or time required to act sustainably is out of reach for many. People are embedded in routines shaped by social norms, material conditions, and available resources. To overcome the value-action-gap –the disconnect between people’s stated values or intentions and their actual practices (Blake, 1999; Mannoni, 2025)– shifts in social and material arrangements that sustain these practices are needed, in ways that rather support than hinder individual values or intentions.

As another respondent put it:

“The cost of living and inflation issues that are happening right across our region and across Europe have (an) impact on people’s participation as they must consider the cost of taking part in this project and the biggest cost of commuting to our study circles.” [Preserving Biodiversity, Ireland, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 76)]

Other examples refer to the struggle to afford heating and electricity, having to make difficult choices about spending:

“if you’ve got a more middle-class community who might have the money to invest in a better heating system and all the rest of it, but people down here, half the houses down here don’t have

⁹ When collecting data on participants’ genders, they were asked to self-identify. We report genders using the terms “man”, “woman” and “non-binary”, in accordance with World Health Organisation guidance on sex and gender terminology. See: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/gender>

gas, don't have any gas pipes going to them (...) they don't have the option.” [Clean Energy, United Kingdom, Retired, 73yo, Man, #DS1 (No. 9)]

Also, high upfront costs, long payback periods, and perceived (or real) affordability challenges hinder the adoption of sustainable technologies (e.g., solar panels, heat pumps):

“Panels on buildings are a sensational thing, but there are also costs, let's not hide them (...), but he first has to spend a lot of money on these panels.” [Clean Energy, Poland, Local Participant, English and Polish language lecturer, 47yo, Woman, #DS1 (No. 9)]

These reflect the lack of a supportive ‘regime’ that would enable financial viability and overcome short-term cost-benefit calculations, which makes it hard for ‘niche’ alternatives to scale. Moreover, these tensions between environmental goals and affordability are also present in our analysis of both code intersections (see Table A3.2, in the Appendix). People are more likely to engage with green solutions when these are framed as ways to save money, rather than purely environmental imperatives.

3.2.2. Insights about ‘environmental crises’

The interview segments coded under ‘**environmental crises**’ depict a socio-technical landscape level marked by the effects of climate change, which often trigger emotionally charged ecological disruptions – from floods and droughts to rapid shifting seasons and biodiversity loss. These events are not abstract concerns but lived experiences in some of the social experiments’ locations and that directly reshape social, economic, and emotional life. Local partners in Slovenia describe their experience with heavy floods at the beginning of August 2023 (four months after the start of the experiments) in several parts of Slovenia, including the Municipality of Ljubljana:

“(...) normal life stopped here for a month. People were in shock of all those unexpected events and experiences. At the same time a lot of charity, help and solidarity was done by people who were not so much affected. (...) A lot of damage (loss of homes, infrastructure – roads, objects, nature – animals, trees, plants, soil etc) occurred (and) affected the cost of life that is now even higher than before.” [Circular Economy, Slovenia, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 19)]

Other participants in the Netherlands refer to extreme weather events during their experiments:

“(...) changing weather patterns with extreme heat followed by extreme precipitation and temperature drops. This had an effect on production and natural cycles.” [Sustainable Food, Netherlands, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 110)]

These quotes convey landscape-level shocks that exert destabilising pressure on regime systems such as agriculture, energy, and mobility. The data also reveals how daily routines and social meanings are reshaped by these pressures – sometimes defensively (e.g., intensifying farming), sometimes creatively (e.g., forming local cooperatives). For example, local partners from Italy noted in their monthly reflections:

“Climate change and the cost of living are putting the agricultural sector at stake. (...) there is the idea that this emergency situation has led most farmers and administration to choose agriculture intensification as a solution. In this context (...) more sustainable practices will be delayed. This pessimist vision might be an obstacle to the social experiment dynamic and its outcomes.” [Sustainable Food, Italy, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 95)]

On the contrary, a participant in the Clean Energy experiments in Spain pointed to emerging community practices:

“So, we started with a motivation to fight climate change, (...) but we see that the community also gives a sense of belonging to the neighbours. (...) We have created a participatory, democratic, open cooperative, a cooperative of the neighbours. We are not supported by any company, we are simply neighbours (...). ...this gives us a common project, a common goal.” [Clean Energy, Spain, Local Participant, Engineer, 45yo, Man, #DS1 (No. 1)]

These examples show that landscape pressures disrupt existing practices but can also catalyse new ones – if infrastructure, shared meanings, and civic capacity align. Still, the emotional weight is palpable. As one respondent reflected: *“Sometimes you panic and think... What can three houses do? You know? A lot actually”* [Efficient Renovations, Ireland, Local Participant, Home Carer, 43yo, Woman, #DS1 (No. 2)]. This underscores the importance of recognising the emotional aspects involved in adapting to environmental crises. It also shows that to resist the pressures imposed by the landscape level, people at the local level (niche) often rely on solidarity and a strong sense of community. The previously mentioned case of floods in Slovenia is a positive example of how charity, solidarity, and community spirit were mobilised to address the crisis. The social experiments have shown how participants actively reshape practices from the ground up, demonstrating both agency and resilience in the face of broader societal challenges. However, it has also shown that not all communities have the resources and capacities to do so, and that structural inequalities and the need for just transitions must be addressed (see more on this point in section 3.3.).

3.2.3. Insights about ‘geopolitical tensions’

In the dataset, **‘geopolitical tensions’** emerge as a landscape-level disruption, influencing practices, institutional trust, and the overall viability of sustainability transitions. The Ukraine–Russia war is the most frequently cited example, described by participants as a destabilising force with tangible effects on energy prices, material supply chains, renovation projects, and emotional security. Furthermore, tensions in the middle east and the war in Gaza are mentioned.

These ‘landscape shocks’ are seen as external forces with far-reaching impacts. As one participant described:

“We have the wars, we have the geopolitics, we have our local situation – I don’t know how prices will change (...) everybody nowadays is worried about their bills.” [Clean Energy, Spain, Local Partner, Sustainable Energy Technician at the Provincial Government of Granada, 47yo, Man, #DS1 (Exit Interview)]

Thus, reflecting the uncertainty that shapes planning and decision-making processes. Such pressures can redirect public focus from long-term transition goals to immediate economic concerns, constraining niche experimentation and challenging regime actors to reconcile demands from both the landscape and emerging grassroots practices. Urgent short-term concerns, triggered by sudden external shocks, as exemplified with geopolitical tensions, can thereby derail sustainability paths towards policy implementation.

Moreover, these geopolitical tensions influence core routines and capacities: rising costs affect materials (e.g. unaffordable retrofits, scarce components), create competence gaps (e.g. inability to plan long-term), alter meanings and reshape emotions (e.g. growing distrust or fear). As one participant put it:

“Fear of investing, fear of all that. Now is the time when we are coming back to calm down a bit.” [Efficient Renovations, Spain, Local Participant, Architect, 55yo, Woman, #DS1 (No. 3)]

Another participant captured the dissonance of jobs versus climate goals due to structural uncertainty that can be reinforced by geopolitical tensions:

“There’s a dissonance... jobs vs. climate goals, and no one says when the coal phase-out will happen.” [Clean Energy, Poland, Local Partner, Project Coordinator, 37yo, Man, #DS1 (Exit Interview)]

These pressures reshape civic responses, including scepticism, (mis)trust in institutions, lack of participation in governance, and understandings of what is politically or socially possible:

“People don’t like things imposed from above... without local dialogue, they just turn away.” [Clean Energy, Poland, Local Participant, English and Polish language lecturer, 47yo, Woman, #DS1 (No. 9)]

The perception of government hesitation creates frustration and confusion at the local level, particularly in energy and transition planning. Meanwhile, niche-level responses such as energy communities show promise but often struggle with institutional fit or limited public understanding, especially in highly regulated sectors:

“Politically we want to move forward, but it’s hard to fit (energy communities) into the current system.” [Clean Energy, Spain, Local Partner, Sustainable Energy Technician at the Provincial Government of Granada, 47yo, Man, #DS1 (Exit Interview)]

We now turn our attention to the drivers, barriers, friction points and windows of opportunity for sustainable transformation, and examine the role of broader societal challenges in shaping these dynamics.

3.3. Societal challenges’ feedback dynamics: drivers, barriers, friction points and windows of opportunity

We used a number of data sources (namely #DS1 – interview codebooks from the experiment streams, as well as #DS2 – monthly surveys and #DS3 – 12th meeting notes) to analyse what was perceived as either a facilitator/accelerator for change towards the Green Deal or what was seen as a hindrance or barrier towards this change. In total, 300 segments were coded as hindrances and 171 as facilitators, suggesting that respondents may perceive more barriers than enabling factors in the dynamics shaped by societal challenges, with a look towards the Green Deal implementation (Table A3.1c in the Appendix).

Divided by social experiment streams, it can be observed in Figure 3.3. that in the stream Sustainable Food the discrepancy between coded segments as *hindrances* and *facilitators* is the largest, with more than 80% of the references being coded as hindrances and less than 20% as facilitators. For the stream Circular Economy, we can observe a similar division, whereas in the stream Preserving Biodiversity slightly more than half of coded segments are *facilitators* and a little less than half are *hindrances*. A similar balanced division between these two categories can be observed in the stream Sustainable Mobility.

Figure 3.3. Percentage of the main societal challenges dynamics per stream (coded segments).
Source: Coding of social experiments interview codebooks for the societal challenges' analysis

These numbers may reflect our previous observations in Figure 3.1b (section 3.1.). For example, the high number of references to hindrances in the Sustainable Food stream can be related to the high number of references to geopolitical tensions in this stream, suggesting the strong impacts for farmers of the Russian – Ukrainian war (e.g. production costs among others) (Rabbi et al. 2023). Similarly, the rise of the cost of living is negatively impacting the overall perception of advancing in achieving the Green Deal's objectives.

In a second round of analysis, we aimed to cluster facilitators and hindrances, guided by our conceptual lens, to better identify the dynamics between levels and find potential windows of opportunity or specify better eventual friction points with regard to change processes aimed at the Green Deal implementation (Box 3.3 below).

Box 3.3. Clusters of drivers and barriers influencing Green Deal implementation

Our analysis revealed the following clusters of drivers and barriers influencing Green Deal implementation, situated across different levels of the socio-technical system:

- **Structural Conditions & Crises** at the landscape level;
- **Policy & Financial Instruments, Administrative Systems, Political & Institutional Alignment,** and **Technical & Professional Support** at the regime level;
- **Community & Social Dynamics** and **Awareness & Values** at the niche level; and
- **Communication & Framing** as a cross-level dynamic.

Importantly, each of these clusters encompasses both facilitating and hindering aspects – highlighting that the same domain (e.g. funding instruments or community dynamics) can either enable or impede progress, depending on context, design, and implementation. For example, within the

cluster *Policy & Financial Instruments (regime)*, subsidies and incentives acted as drivers when aligned with people's immediate needs (e.g. saving energy costs), but became hindrances when access was difficult, bureaucratic, or delayed – particularly for those hit hardest by the cost of living or financial insecurity (*landscape*). This complexity challenges a simplistic equation of facilitators with 'windows of opportunity' and hindrances with 'friction points'. Facilitators can enable action, but windows of opportunity arise only when structural, institutional, and motivational conditions converge¹⁰. These windows may be crisis-driven (e.g., energy inflation), policy-triggered (e.g., new subsidies), or socially constructed (e.g., local mobilization). As an example of the latter, in the Sustainable Food experiments in Košice, Slovakia, the school community worked to improve school food procurement by involving local producers and civic actors. While national procurement rules were rigid, the experiment succeeded in bringing institutional actors into dialogue, laying the groundwork for potential policy change at the municipal level. This is an example of a niche-level experiment creating pressure for change at the regime-level.

However, windows of opportunity are not neutral and might have unaccountable consequences, depending on the context. What can be an opportunity for some, may be a barrier for others.

Conversely, friction points are not just static obstacles. They are systemic misalignments – between policy design and everyday life practices, between institutional tools and lived capacities. They appear in bureaucratic delays, institutional inertia, or in cultural tensions and distrust. They persist even when opportunities technically exist.

Societal challenges as landscape-pressures can make it therefore even more relevant to strengthen resilience and response-capacities on all systems levels to these complex dynamics. The example of the lived experience of floods in Slovenia during the Circular Economy experiments provides a positive case of response-capacity on a niche level in terms of solidarity and charity, fortifying mutual help and social bonds, which are vital to overcome temporary hardship and build up long-term trust and resilience. Another positive example is the energy cooperative run by neighbours in Granada, Spain (Clean Energy stream) that people built up to combat climate change, having overcome diverse initial opposing forces from the regime level. Their common goal and sense of belonging enhanced their response capacity and resilience against setbacks. When aligned well with regime-responses, such environmental pressures can constitute a window of opportunity for transformative change. Anticipatory governance mechanisms (Boyd et al., 2015; Muiderman et al., 2022) can give orientation on how to navigate and better respond to new windows of opportunity for transformation as well as to adequately address the friction points impeding to move forward. Studies in this field underline the importance of stakeholder integration with active participation and adaptive forms of governance (Boyd et al., 2015). The next section about actors can provide further details in this sense.

¹⁰ COVID-19 was seen as a window of opportunity for sustainability transitions and change towards more sustainable behaviour (Bodenheimer & Leidenberger, 2020) at the beginning of the pandemic, however, from today's perspective we observe that the structural, institutional and motivational conditions did not align to foster the necessary change, with rather increasingly unsustainable behaviour, as demonstrated in the SDGs monitoring reports (Sachs et al., 2024), making the Agenda 2030 difficult to achieve.

3.4. The main actors to drive transformative change towards a strong Green Deal

To identify the main actors who are driving change across the SHARED GREEN DEAL's social experiments, we first inductively identified all actors that were mentioned in the data (see Figure 3.4a below and Table A3.4 for detailed actor subcodes in the Appendix).

Figure 3.4a. Percentage of actors coded segments (n=830)

Source: Interview codebooks (#DS1), Monthly Surveys (#DS2) and 12th Meeting Notes (#DS3).

In the next step of our analysis, we adapted the pressure matrix (Morone et al. 2016) by conceptualizing the landscape level as composed of both global and local actors exerting pressure through political and economic channels, applying this matrix to the actors identified in our first step. Our findings suggest that transformational change is driven not by isolated actors, but through what Morone et al. (2016) describe as a 'combined pressure mechanism', where multiple, independently acting sources reinforce one another. These pressures can be grouped by two main axes of analysis – global or local and economic or political channels of pressure – which constitute a stakeholder matrix (see Figure 3.4b). We then reflect on each actor's group and their position within this pressure matrix, and how they can support achieving the Green Deal objectives.

Figure 3.4b. Actors pressure matrix.
Source: Adapted by the authors based on Morone et al. (2016)

EU institutions

EU institutions, positioned in the horizontal stretch between economic and political pressures and vertically under global pressures, are the core actors for the EU’s funding and financing mechanisms, as shown by the EU’s mission approach (section 1.3), and provide financial support and guidance for sustainability projects. However, many small, rural municipalities lack the administrative capacity (e.g. lack of human resources, language barriers) and upfront capital to access and utilise EU funds, even when the funding covers a high percentage of project costs.

“We need to find a way to get more participation from councilors, mayors, and also municipal technicians, secretaries, and controllers, of course (...) I feel that a lot of it has been about the electricity sector, regulations, how we can apply the existing regulations to actually meet what Europe is telling us we need to do at the European, national, and regional levels.” [Clean Energy, Spain, Local Partner, Lawyer (energy communities specialized), 58yo, Woman, #DS1 (No. 10)]

The bureaucratic requirements and the lack of flexibility in EU funding for operational and social aspects, rather than just investments, creates barriers for these resource-constrained local governments. Moreover, some national governments are showing resistance to EU-driven green energy initiatives and the European Green Deal, seeking to ease the pressure and slow the implementation of these policies. Additionally, there is a disconnect between the EU’s broader, geopolitical priorities and perspectives, and the more localised, short-term concerns of citizens and municipalities. The EU struggles to effectively communicate the rationale and long-term importance of its

policies to these stakeholders (e.g. rural populations), who may be resistant to changes perceived as imposed from above.

National and local governments

Governments at national and local levels can provide financial incentives, subsidies, and support programs to facilitate the transition towards the Green Deal, such as renovation grants, and tax breaks for businesses and households adopting more sustainable practices. However, short-term thinking and prioritising political interests over long-term environmental and social goals can be observed.

“And we have been looking to our government to provide cheap loans, you know, for renovations (...) Time goes on, and time goes on, and that’s things that promise. But they don’t come, you know. They haven’t come so far, but that is kind of disappointing that we could save people” [Efficient Renovations, Ireland, Local Partner, #DS3]

The lack of political will, insufficient budget allocation, and inconsistent or unpredictable policies can hinder progress and aggravate disconnections between national-level policies and local-level implementation, e.g. some governments are not prioritising issues such as energy efficiency, energy poverty, and sustainable agriculture, contributing thereby to crises to endure.

The private sector

Multinational corporations exert global economic pressure on the local actors through their market power and influence over supply chains. Larger companies, such as those in the food industry, can also have an influence that may not always align with sustainability goals.

“(...) the food system is incredibly linked to, to the big players in the food industry, like directly linked to the business sector (...) all of them sit on far too many positions where they have too much power simply. They should not have that power. It is very strange.” [Sustainable Food, Sweden, Local Participant, Real estate, 45yo, Woman, #DS1 (No. 5)]

Multinational corporations also can use their economic power and influence to hinder the advancement of energy communities and other local renewable energy initiatives. There is a perceived lack of community benefit from large-scale renewable energy projects, and a sense that big energy companies are making profits at the expense of consumers through high tariffs and a lack of local investment. Meanwhile businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, while still behind in adopting Circular Economy practices, can be drivers of change if they are provided with the right support and incentives. Some companies are interested in adopting Circular Economy practices, as working with recycled materials can result in lower prices, but they often struggle with the high costs and difficulties of waste management and sustainable production practices. Entrepreneurs also prioritise financial viability and profitability over other societal concerns, unless there are clear economic incentives or legal requirements that compel them to act in a more socially or environmentally friendly manner.

Producers

Producers, particularly local farmers, are caught between the need to adapt to environmental concerns and the economic realities of maintaining their livelihoods. Globally, they experience economic pressure from powerful retailers who control the supply chain and limit their access to consumers. Moreover, they may be hindered by the rigidity of conventional farming practices, fear of economic losses, and lack of support or incentives to adopt more sustainable methods. Targeting younger farmers and strengthening existing communities of sustainable-oriented producers can help overcome these barriers.

“Let’s say the main issue regarding the use of pesticides that emerged was the rigidity of the producers, the farmers, to change methods. They are afraid of losing money, afraid it won’t work, and they are used to doing things this way, especially the older ones (...) The solution we found is to focus more on the young and on people who are already somewhat inclined towards this topic.”
[Sustainable Food, Italy, Local Participant, University Researcher in Sociology, 34yo, Woman, #DS1 (No. 2)]

Media

The media are positioned as powerful agenda-setters that shape public narratives, political discourse, and the perceived legitimacy of Green Deal measures. They can play a critical enabling role by translating complex transition goals into accessible stories, amplifying local innovations, and holding governments accountable. However, their influence is double-edged: the media can also reinforce polarisation, focus disproportionately on controversy or individual behaviour, and neglect systemic dimensions of change. In times of crisis – such as energy shocks or climate disasters – media framing can either open or close public windows of opportunity, intensifying friction points.

“I mean there is another thing: that the media are showing a lot of themes about the problem of the waste management of textile. So there are many things that have run. So it has helped to push this solution brought by the association.” [Circular Economy, France, Local Partner, #DS3]

Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

CSOs and NGOs exert political pressure to leverage their visibility and funding to support local communities, particularly vulnerable groups, by channelling their professional expertise to influence the design of government support programs (e.g. for energy-poor households). However, they often face challenges in their advocacy efforts, as governments may be unwilling to collaborate with them or make unpredictable decisions that hinder their work. In some cases, however, CSOs and NGOs find more success in engaging with local authorities – who are more receptive to their input and proposals than national authorities.

“The political situation in Slovakia is unstable and challenging for NGOs. The Ministry of Environment is making unpredictable decisions (...) There is also a narrative that ‘NGOs cannot dictate to the government what to do’ so advocacy activities are a challenge. We believe, that we can make some changes on the municipal level since for Košice City and Košice Region the situation is not that bad and we have the door open to discussions with the local councils.”
[Sustainable Food, Slovakia, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 101)]

Similarly, different types of associations seek greater commitment and support from local authorities. They emphasise the importance of political will to listen to and engage with diverse stakeholders, not just those who are like-minded, in order to move society forward collectively.

Cooperatives constitute another relevant format, since they provide a legal structure and common project for local communities, allowing them to collectively address societal challenges. These cooperatives also engage the younger generation and give community members a vested interest in their own future, empowering them to shape local solutions. However, there are economic pressures that stem from the difficulties in financing and managing projects (e.g. energy communities), as well as the need to achieve sufficient scale to make them economically viable.

Schools (students, teachers and parents)

In the Sustainable Mobility and Food streams we noted that young people are increasingly aware of and concerned about issues like climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation. They can put pressure on political leaders and policymakers to take bolder action to address

these challenges. Young people are also using economic channels, such as boycotting unsustainable products and services while they can also be actively and politically engaged in projects and initiatives that aim to improve their immediate living environment. However, they sometimes feel that their voices are not being heard or taken seriously by local decision-makers.

“They’re all very conscious of climate effects, and there is a lot of anxiety with the students around what they can do, but they certainly feel that their voice is missing, they feel that there’s a disconnect between them and I suppose the political powers (...) I think they really relished that opportunity to make their own voices hear.” [Sustainable Mobility, Ireland, Local Participant, School Teacher, 42yo, Man, #DS1 (No. 1)]

In the Sustainable Mobility stream, teachers promoted low-impact transport and environmental education, actively engaging with students, parents, and community groups to develop sustainability projects that connect youth and adult perspectives.

Parents often prefer faster, more convenient transport modes like private cars due to safety and convenience concerns, despite children’s interest in sustainable options. However, when involved in school sustainability projects, parents tend to become more supportive of environmentally friendly and more healthy, independent travel choices.

“Parents also welcome the idea because, as I said, most families live in the neighbourhood, and it is important for them to have a safe environment for their children to move around too. Perhaps that is one of the reasons why they accompany them all the time with their own transport.” [Sustainable Mobility, Bulgaria, Local Participant, Teacher, Woman, #DS1 (No. 4)]

Citizens and Consumers

Citizens¹¹, situated under local and political pressure, are both subjects of transition policies and potential agents of change. Across the experiments, their role was shaped not only by individual motivation or awareness, but by structural conditions – access to information, trust in institutions, housing status, and everyday constraints. Participation varied: some citizens actively engaged through community energy projects, repair initiatives, or school-led actions; others felt sidelined or overwhelmed, especially in contexts marked by economic precarity or bureaucratic opacity. Citizens’ capacity to act meaningfully depends on how systems recognise, support, and respond to their situated needs. Consumers also play a role, as their acquisition practices are influenced by cost, social pressure, loss of purchasing power – since some consumers are highly price-sensitive and often prioritize immediate cost savings over long-term environmental benefits. Amid rising costs, many struggle with high energy bills, especially those in low-income or poorly insulated homes. In the Circular Economy stream, while there is increasing receptiveness to buying second-hand, the perception that eco-friendly products should be cheaper remains a challenge.

“People are increasingly receptive to buying second-hand. This is related to inflation which remains high and is having an impact on consumers. It is also related to the many media like on ARTE tv related to fast fashion. So it is an opportunity for us.” [Circular Economy, France, Local Participant, Home and Office Organizer and Zero Waste upcycler, 43yo, Woman (No. 7)]

Landlords and tenants

In the Clean Energy stream’s experiments in the UK and Poland, landlords were hesitant to invest in energy upgrades, especially when costs were high and benefits accrued to tenants – a classic case of split incentives. Furthermore, tenants – especially in low-income or precarious situations – sometimes lack the means, agency, or information to demand improvements or navigate renovation schemes. These tensions were particularly visible in communities facing multiple pressures

11 In this group we include all the social experiments’ target groups as specified in Table A1.1 (see the Appendix).

– rising costs, poor housing stock, and weak institutional support. Without mechanisms to align economic incentives and clarify responsibilities, this actor group remains structurally constrained from contributing to Green Deal objectives.

“I think people tend to try not to think too much about those kinds of things because they haven’t got the money to do it and it’s up to somebody else. They’ve got the idea it’s up to somebody else to solve their problem. It’s up to my landlord to put my central heating in. That is somebody else’s problem.” [Clean Energy, United Kingdom, Local Participant, Retired, 73yo, Man, #DS1 (No. 9)]

Professional experts

Experts, such as architects, engineers, and renovation specialists, play a crucial role in advising and supporting individuals and communities on energy efficiency and sustainability measures. They provide technical expertise, practical guidance that supports the shaping of everyday practices related to home improvements, renewable energy, and other sustainability initiatives, and financial information to help people reduce their energy consumption and costs – which is particularly valuable for low-income households and communities, where energy poverty is a significant challenge. However, experts face the challenge of translating technical information in ways that align with everyday practices, while navigating deep rooted routines and socio-material conditions that hinder the uptake of information and its application in practice. And while experts’ role is crucial, their impact is often limited by political and institutional barriers, such as lack of political will. Moreover, a shortage of these professionals, especially in certain regions, can also be a barrier to sustainability transitions.

“But when a professional explains to me what I’m going to get, what I’m going to see from it (...) and they even explained what I was going to do in the first winter and how much extra money I was going to have in my pocket – I think there’s no reason to doubt.” [Efficient Renovations, Hungary, Local Participant, President of the Nógrád County Roma Local Government, 47yo, Man, #DS1 (No. 5)]

Non-human actors

We also observed the importance of non-human actors, such as socio-material infrastructure, natural elements and exogenous shocks triggered by coronavirus (i.e. SARS-CoV-2). Below, a quote illustrates how the spread of a type of beetle, allegedly driven by climate change, raised concerns among farmers and prompted increased pesticide use.

*“An increase in the use of pesticides was registered due to the spread of *Popillia japonica* – a Japanese beetle that has no predators in Italy – in the last month (...) The spread of this and other pests is also linked to climate change and the exceptionally warm periods during the spring and the summer.”* [Sustainable Food, Italy, Local Partner, #DS2 (No. 92)]

Barriers are embedded in the socio-material infrastructure, including inadequate or insufficient bike lanes, perceived safety risks (namely among women and adolescent girls (see the report on the SSH priority theme Gender in this collection (Aggeli et al., 2025)), and the way convenience is built into existing mobility practices. The improvement and expansion of local infrastructures, such as bike lanes, depend heavily on municipal decisions, while cultural norms and policy inertia (e.g. car-centric urbanism) create friction. Electric vehicles and renewable energy sources are also seen as potential solutions to reduce the environmental impact of transportation and energy production, however, the high cost of these technologies was noted as a barrier to wider adoption.

“We look at what the options are, what condition the property is in, what makes sense, what doesn’t, what you have access to – for example, is there gas in the street or the flat, is there a possibility of solar panels, what condition the walls, windows, and doors are in, and how much

money is available for renovation. [Efficient Renovations, Hungary, Local Participant, Project Manager, 52yo, Man, #DS1 (No. 7)]

Moreover, natural elements like trees, animals, and plants emerged as meaningful non-human actors, not only shaping awareness but also influencing decisions and actions – for example, prompting efforts to preserve habitats or restore green spaces. Participants recognised the importance of biodiversity and the negative impacts of pollution and urban development. In the Preserving Biodiversity stream, this translated into concerns about habitat loss and a push to enhance biodiversity through tree planting and wildlife-friendly initiatives.

4. Learning points and recommendations for policy and governance

In this section we summarise what we learned from our secondary data analysis (section 4.1) and provide some recommendations for policy and governance (section 4.2) that are targeted to enhance the response-capacity of various stakeholders to societal challenges.

4.1. Learning points about societal challenges

Societal challenges disrupt – but can also mobilise – transitions

Landscape-level shocks, such as military conflicts, wars, and other geopolitical tensions often shift attention from long-term planning to short-term priorities ('survival mode'). Rising energy and food prices, supply chain disruptions, and escalating tensions created uncertainty across many of the experiments. Coordinated action and long-term planning is made more difficult – a dynamic that can be referred to as 'survival-mode pragmatism', as experienced in the Circular Economy stream regarding local market structures and cost-driven decision making:

"It is difficult to convince consumers. Cost to the buyer is the only thing that matters at the end of the day." [Circular Economy, Cyprus Local Participant, Civil Engineer, 39yo, Man, #DS1 (No. 2)]

This is an illustration of a 'push back' or 'temporary retreat' that may derail policy implementation. However, simultaneously, there were also signs of 'pushing back against the push back'¹². Thus, we also observed how strong local networks and shared purpose enabled communities to respond effectively, even in resource-constrained settings, as exemplified by the previously mentioned cases of solidarity as flood-reactions in Slovenia or the energy cooperative in Granada, Spain (section 3.3). Niche-actors can demonstrate strong response-capacities, which should be enhanced by regime-level support. When niche-level action is aligned with broader governance structures, societal challenges can force the opening of windows of opportunity – but only if met with the capacity to anticipate and coordinate action across system levels.

Align policy tools with everyday realities

Many regime-level interventions – such as subsidies, grant schemes, or public awareness campaigns – fell short because they were poorly aligned with daily practices. Barriers included complex bureaucratic procedures, inadequate infrastructure, or a lack of trusted intermediaries to help people navigate programmes. In the Sustainable Mobility stream, for instance, a young participant described the difficulty of using public transport from remote areas – highlighting how material conditions (e.g. housing location, service availability) constrain even well-intentioned choices:

¹² Contributions by Hans Bruyninckx at the International Transitions Conference 2025, see plenary panel debate on 'Transition Policy and Role of Transition Research', (Dinâmia'CET-Iscte, 2025) as well as his paper in parallel session 7.1 on Destabilization Policy and Programmes (Bruyninckx, 2025).

“Well, because we live very far away and Mum tries to use public transport more, but things don’t always work out because we live really far away.” [Sustainable Mobility, Bulgaria, Local Participant, Student, 10yo, Girl, #DS1 (No. 7)]

This misalignment underscores the need for policy mechanisms that are not only technically sound but socially embedded, responsive to context, and designed with diverse social groups in mind.

Values, emotions, and solidarity are critical capacities

Transitions are not only technical; they are also emotional and cultural processes. The experiments revealed that societal challenges can evoke fatigue, fear, anxiety or apathy – but also inspire acts of care, resilience, and creativity:

“(…) for example, I want to be part of an energy community because I care deeply about my neighbourhood, because I see that there are tremendous pollution problems, and because I believe that energy should be managed by us, much better than by people who do not understand the reality of our towns.” [Clean Energy, Spain, Local Participant, Secondary Education Teacher, 43yo, Man, #DS1 (No. 2)]

Recognising these emotional dynamics is essential for building long-term systems’ resilience. Emotional engagement, trust, and shared narratives are not ‘soft’ dimensions; they are central components of a system’s capacity to anticipate, absorb, and adapt to shocks.

4.2. Policy and Governance Recommendations

To enhance response-capacity and systemic resilience at both the regime and niche levels, we propose the following policy and governance recommendations:

1. Embed Anticipatory Governance into Transition Strategies

Establish anticipatory governance mechanisms that help institutions and communities detect, interpret, and act on early signals of disruption or opportunity.

These should be participatory and adaptive, integrating diverse voices and lived knowledge to avoid top-down blind spots (Muiderman et al., 2022).

Support regular scenario-building, community foresight workshops (e.g. visioning), and flexible program design.

2. Strengthen Institutional Responsiveness and Local Intermediation

Regime actors must develop agile delivery systems that allow for fast adaptation in the face of changing conditions – particularly for funding, renovation, and mobility programs.

Invest in trusted intermediaries (e.g. renovation advisors, local coordinators) to connect formal systems with niche actors, especially in vulnerable or remote areas.

Simplify procedures and improve institutional continuity to build public trust and engagement.

3. Support Niche-Level Innovation and Collective Capacity

Provide stable, long-term support (not just pilots) for grassroots initiatives that have demonstrated capacity to mobilise local actors and experiment with sustainable solutions.

Expand funding, infrastructure access, and legal protections for community energy projects, Circular Economy initiatives, and social enterprises.

Recognise and support further informal social capacities – like care, mutual aid, and peer learning – as critical resources for transition resilience, e.g. stimulated through life-long-learning programmes, volunteering and similar initiatives.

4. Align Incentives and Infrastructure with Everyday Practices

Design policies that recognise the material and social arrangements that shape everyday practices – such as transport networks, housing access, or digital connectivity.

Link transition policies to daily life improvements – not only climate metrics – especially in areas affected by economic pressure or social fragmentation.

Regularly involve citizens in their role as end-users in the co-design of programs to ensure practical relevance and uptake.

Take into account both living and non-living non-human actors – like nature, weather, buildings, and transport infrastructure – when identifying barriers or facilitators that affect people's ability to engage in sustainable practices.

5. Reframe Transition Narratives and Rebuild Political Trust

Improve communication from EU and national institutions by focusing on clear, relatable benefits, long-term purpose, and fairness, considering particularly vulnerable groups.

Promote visible, accessible stories of local success – such as energy cooperatives or school-based projects¹³ – to counter narratives of exclusion or imposition.

Encourage municipal-level storytelling and shared learning to connect different places facing similar challenges.

¹³ See e.g. the reports on findings and recommendations of each social experiment stream of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project: (i) Clean Energy (Gray et al. 2025b); (ii) Circular Economy (Ruiz et al., 2025); (iii) Efficient Renovations (Foulds et al., 2025b), (iv) Sustainable Food (Beers et al., 2025), (v) Sustainable Mobility (Haufe & Tönkö, 2025); (vi) Preserving Biodiversity (Šmid Hribar et al., 2025).

5. Conclusions

This report is one of five reports on SSH priority themes addressing the *Societal Challenges Post COVID-19* drawing on a secondary data analysis collected during 24 social experiments carried out within the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. Following the main goal to analyse how societal challenges can drive, accelerate, or hinder progress in implementing the Green Deal, we answered three research questions that targeted (i) patterns and interrelationship dynamics, (ii) feedback dynamics (i.e. what were the facilitators to and hindrances of change observed and how were responses to societal challenges shaped), and (iii) the actors of driving such change towards the Green Deal implementation. We applied a (combined) conceptual lens guided by Sustainability Transitions Theories, in particular the Multi-Level-Perspective (Geels, 2002,2024), complemented by Social Practice Theory (Keller et al., 2022; Shove et al., 2012), as these were found useful to interpret system dynamics, interrelationships and feedback loops across the social experiments' streams.

Through the data sources, we found that societal challenges – identified in the data as rising cost of living, environmental crises, and geopolitical tensions – acted as 'landscape' pressures that shaped both opportunities and obstacles across the streams. These pressures prompted in some cases short-term coping practices (e.g. observed in various streams in the form of cost-sensitive acquisition practices, reduced participation and political will, or reliance on immediate practical solutions), but also triggered local innovation, particularly where community cohesion, trust, and targeted support mechanisms were present (e.g. in the Sustainable Mobility stream in Bulgaria).

While each thematic stream dealt with its own sectoral specificities, common patterns emerged. For example, the Clean Energy, Efficient Renovations, and Sustainable Mobility streams all encountered infrastructural and affordability barriers, revealing how cost of living, and spatial inequalities, constrain sustainable practices. In Circular Economy and Sustainable Food, participants highlighted value tensions – between affordability and environmental concern, or between institutional norms and local innovation. The Preserving Biodiversity stream added a distinctive emphasis on relational care, local knowledge, and the emotional dimensions of ecological engagement.

Feedback loops emerged between the niche and regime levels – for instance, when grassroots innovations showed potential to inspire policy shifts (e.g. in the Sustainable Food experiments in Košice, Slovakia, by bringing institutional actors into dialogue to change rigid school meals procurement rules), or when regime-level failures triggered community self-organisation (e.g. in the Clean Energy experiments in Granada, Spain, where a neighbour-led energy cooperative overcame initial institutional resistance and eventually gained recognition and support from local government). These dynamics highlight that societal challenges are not mere external disruptions, they have the capacity to shape the various systems (e.g. food, energy, mobility) from within, often unevenly across temporal and geographical contexts.

Regarding final reflections and implications, the report shows that the social experiments as niche-initiatives were confronted with global pressures that can create instability, reinforce inequality further, and cause emotional strain. Whether societal challenges accelerate or hinder sustainability transitions depends on how systems respond – across governance, institutions, and communities.

Key findings suggest that:

Local response-capacity can be strong, especially when built on trust, solidarity, and ownership;

Regime-level alignment is essential to sustain and scale grassroots efforts¹⁴ on scaling perspectives of the social experiments);

Anticipatory governance and participatory, adaptive mechanisms are needed to navigate uncertainty and respond to emerging windows of opportunity and overcome friction points.

And that **structural barriers** – including access to funding, infrastructure, and recognition – must be addressed to avoid exacerbating existing inequalities.

Importantly, the feedback dynamics between actors and across system levels show that no transition occurs in isolation. Thematic solutions (e.g. energy, food, mobility) are deeply interconnected, and should be approached through integrated, multi-sectoral strategies (e.g. nexus thinking). Enhancing response-capacity and systemic resilience requires policies that are aligned with everyday practices, inclusive of both human and non-human actors, and capable of bridging short-term needs with long-term transformation goals.

14 See the report on D5.1 SSH priority theme Geographic Differences (Nieboer et al., 2025), in this collection.

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Appendix

Table A1.1. Social experiments profiles

#	Priority area (thematic stream)	Approach	Target group	Place of social experiment	Local partner organisation	Context (rural/urban)*
1	Clean Energy	Community visioning	Policymakers, businesses, local communities	Granada, Spain	Local authority (Diputación de Granada)	mix
				Bełchatów, Poland	NGO (Polish Green Network)	mix
				Jaywick, UK	Local authority (Essex County Council)	rural
				Ærø, Marstal, Denmark	NGO (Fonden Motorfabrikken Marstal and Blue Innovators)	rural
2	Circular Economy	Local accelerator hubs	Local businesses, academics, authorities, and NGOs	Santo Tirso, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Santo Tirso)	urban
				Val-de-Marne, France	NGO (Val de Marne en Transition)	urban
				Nicosia/Limassol/Larnaca, Cyprus	National authority (Cyprus Organization for Standardization)	mix
				Ljubljana, Slovenia	Local authority (Technology Park Ljubljana)	urban
3	Efficient Renovations	Knowledge networks on energy renovation and eco-home-tours	Under-represented and marginalised groups and renovation professionals (40-60% women)	Zaragoza, Spain	NGO (ECODES Zaragoza)	urban
				Nógrád County, Hungary	NGO (Habitat for Humanity Hungary)	rural
				Vilnius, Lithuania	Local authority (Let's Renovate the City Vilnius)	urban
				Louisburgh, Mayo County, Ireland	Regional authority (Mayo County Council Louisburgh)	rural
4	Sustainable Mobility	School mobility labs	Per experiment 30 young people (aged 10-16) and 5 to 10 stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and school administrators	Braga, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Braga)	urban
				Galway, Ireland	NGO (Am Meitheal Rothar Ireland)	urban
				Panevėžys, Lithuania	NGO (ECAT Lithuania)	urban
				Sofia, Bulgaria	NGO (Sofia Development Association Bulgaria)	urban
5	Sustainable Food	Local food Assemblies	Young people aged 18-35 years	Stockholm, Sweden	NGO (REFORMATEN)	urban
				Cella Monte, Italy	NGO (ASFODELO)	rural
				Košice, Slovakia	NGO (Klíma ěa potrebuje)	mix
				Wageningen, Netherlands	NGO (Gemeente Wageningen)	mix
6	Preserving Biodiversity	Study Circles	Diverse group of 10-15 adults per Study Circle (ensure diversity in age, gender, occupation and social vulnerability)	Tolmin, Slovenia	NGO (Posoški razvojni center)	rural
				Amaroussion, Greece	Local authority (Municipality of Amaroussion)	urban
				Kilfinane, Ireland	NGO (Ballyhoura Development CLG)	rural
				Stockholm, Sweden	Local authority (Environment and Health Department of the Municipality of Stockholm)	urban

*Note: Rural/urban is based on European Commission (2014), A harmonised definition of Cities and Rural Areas: The new Degree of Urbanisation.

Table A1.2. Data sources collected from social experiments considered for the secondary analysis

Data source (#DS)	Provided by	Comment / Description
#DS1: WP4 Codebooks of interview data with social experiments participants ¹⁵	SGD consortium members (WP4)	Interviews were conducted by local partners with a variety of participants in social experiments (respecting representative selection criteria), then transcribed and analysed by consortium members. The analysis was guided by specific codes relevant for SSH priority themes - defined ahead - and organized per social experiment stream (Circular Economy, Clean Energy, Efficient Renovation, Sustainable Food, Sustainable Mobility, Preserving Biodiversity), resulting in six codebooks. Per stream, 10 interviews of approx. 30-60 min. were conducted (240 in total).
#DS2: Monthly survey (WP5 questions)	Local partners	At the end of each month, local partners filled in a monthly survey about the ongoing experiments that was prepared by the consortium partners, directed already towards SSH priority themes. (288 surveys in total).
#DS3: Monthly meeting notes (including 12th meeting)	SGD consortium members	Consortium members met with the local partners of each experiment monthly and took note of the developments and progress in the social experiments. For each experiment, the 12th meeting note summarizes all meetings of the past 12 months and reflects on the whole process.
#DS4: Final reflective surveys and experiments' journeys (Responsible Research & innovation (RRI) material)	Local partners	Local partners were given an extensive reflection survey, that included a narrative /qualitative part in which they were asked to reflect and describe the journey of their experiments (24 surveys and 24 experiment journey files (reflections by local partners).
#DS5: RRI interviews with consortium partners	SGD consortium members	The team of WP 6 - Impact evaluation and RRI integration conducted interviews with respective consortium members of each experiment's stream. (6 interviews in total).
#DS6: Applications of Local Partners to host social experiments	Local partners	Shared Green Deal's call for application to host social experiments in the six Green Deal priorities areas received 344 applications in which the candidate organizations (NGO's, association, local authorities (municipalities) detailed how they would conduct the experiments and assure qualitative criteria (i.e. inclusive approach) and commit to previous training provided by the project.
#DS7: Green Deal Topic Webinars	SGD consortium members	Project partners held webinars on each Green Deal priority topic, describing the respective social experiment journeys (https://sharedgreendeal.eu/multimedia/playlist-local-actions-shared-green-deal).

¹⁵ Due to the nature of the qualitative data, openly sharing full datasets would risk compromising participant anonymity. However, anonymised interview transcripts for #DS1 and for each of the six experiment streams are available and can be accessed at the Zenodo platform, community SHARED GREEN DEAL. For **Circular Economy**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Circular Economy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387249>; for **Clean Energy**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Clean Energy [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15274546>; for **Efficient Renovations**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Efficient Renovations [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076033>; for **Sustainable Food**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Sustainable Food [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387236>; for **Sustainable Mobility**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Sustainable Mobility [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15325897>; for **Preserving Biodiversity**: SHARED GREEN DEAL. (2025). Interviews with SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiment Participants - Preserving Biodiversity [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076035>.

Figure A2.1. Multi-level perspective on socio-technical transitions
Source: Geels (2024)

Table A3.1a. Societal challenges code frequency (coded segments) per data source (#DS)

Data sources	Environmental crises	Cost of living	Geopolitical tensions	Total
Interview Codebooks	281	313	114	708
Monthly Surveys	41	55	62	158
12th Meeting Notes	19	32	49	100
Total	341	400	225	966

Source: Interview codebooks (#DS1), Monthly Surveys (#DS2) and 12th Meeting Notes (#DS3)

Table A3.1b. Societal challenges code frequency (coded segments) per stream and data source (#DS)

Societal challenges	Circular Economy	Clean Energy	Efficient Renovations	Preserving Biodiversity	Sustainable Food	Sustainable Mobility	Total
Interview Codebooks							
Environmental crises	11	73	11	50	5	131	281
Cost of living	46	91	112	7	23	34	313
Geopolitical tensions	17	37	18	3	14	25	114
Subtotal	74	201	141	60	42	190	708
Monthly Surveys							
Environmental crises	9	5	5	7	10	5	41
Cost of living	11	10	17	3	11	3	55
Geopolitical tensions	10	13	19	5	9	6	62
Subtotal	30	28	41	15	30	14	158
12th Meeting Notes							
Environmental crises	2	4	2	3	6	2	19
Cost of living	4	15	3	1	4	5	32
Geopolitical tensions	4	10	6	6	17	6	49
Subtotal	10	29	11	10	27	13	100
Total	114	258	193	85	99	217	966

Source: Interview codebooks (#DS1), Monthly Surveys (#DS2) and 12th Meeting Notes (#DS3)

Table A3.1c. Categories and code description and frequencies (coded segments)

Categories and codes	Description	n
Societal challenges patterns	Segments which mention the absence of societal challenges reporting (i.e. missing)	39
Environmental crises	Segments which mention social, economic and political dynamics that impact European contemporary societies such as the biodiversity crisis, climate change and sustainable infrastructure	341
Cost of living	Segments which mention social, economic and political dynamics that impact European contemporary societies e.g. economic pressure on small business, inflation and interest rates	400
Geopolitical tensions	Segments which mention the social, economic and political dynamics that are impacting European contemporary societies such as the Ukraine war, the political tensions and uncertainties and supply chain disruptions	225
Dynamic		
Hinder	Segments which mention societal challenges hindering the achievement of the Green Deal objectives	300
Facilitator/accelerator	Segments which mention societal challenges facilitating or accelerating the achievement of the Green Deal objectives	171
Actors	Open sub-coding of this code according to the actors that emerge from the data (see Table A3.4)	830

Source: Interview codebooks (#DS1), Monthly Surveys (#DS2) and 12th Meeting Notes (#DS3)

Table A3.1d. Societal challenges code frequency (coded segments) per Green Deal stream

Societal challenges codes	SHARED GREEN DEAL Streams						Total
	Circular Economy	Clean Energy	Efficient Renovations	Sustainable Food	Sustainable Mobility	Preserving Biodiversity	
Environmental crises	11	73	11	5	131	50	281
Cost of living	46	91	112	23	34	7	313
Geopolitical tensions	17	37	18	14	25	3	114
Total	74	201	141	42	190	61	708

Source: Interview codebooks (#DS1)

Table A3.2. Intersections¹⁶ between societal challenges codes frequency (coded segments)

Societal challenges codes	Environmental crises	Cost of living	Geopolitical tensions
Environmental crises	0	31	13
Cost of living	31	0	16
Geopolitical tensions	13	16	0

Source: Interview codebooks (#DS1)

Table A3.4. Overview of actors and actors groups identified in our data analysis

Actors and actor groups							
Private sector (general, unspecified)	60	Civil society (general, unspecified)	26	Non-human (non-living)		Non-human (living)	
▪ Companies	50	▪ NGOs	11	<i>Material</i>		<i>Nature</i>	
• Brands	3	▪ Associations	12	▪ Vehicles		▪ Fungi	2
▪ Entrepreneurs	3	▪ Cooperatives	9	• Cars	43	▪ Plants	9
▪ Banks	8	▪ Energy communities	29	♦ Electric cars	2	▪ Animals	4
▪ Landlords	5	▪ Experts	12	• Scooters	6	• Pests	4
▪ Producers	5	▪ Consumers	38	• Bicycles	25	• Beetles	3
• Farmers	31	▪ Young people	48	▪ Public transport	10	• Bees	3
Media	8	• Children	27	Infrastructure		• Birds	4
Government (general, unspecified)	53	• Teenagers	3	▪ Solar panels	15	• Butterflies	1
▪ Political parties	5	▪ Tenants	3	▪ Power plants	13	▪ SARS-COV-2	15
▪ Local government	73	▪ Parents	27				
▪ Central government	19	▪ Schools	52				
▪ EU	25	• Students	21				
		• Teachers	5				

Source: Interview codebooks (#DS1), Monthly Surveys (#DS2) and 12th Meeting Notes (#DS3).

16 For this analysis we consider the intersection of codes in the same coded segment.

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